

ИНСОН ҲУҚУҚЛАРИ БЎЙИЧА ХАЛҚАРО СТАНДАРТЛАРНИ МИЛЛИЙ ҚОНУНЧИЛИККА ЖОРИЙ ҚИЛИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ

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ИИВ Академияси, Давлат-ҳуқуқий фанлар ва инсон ҳуқуқларини таъминлаш кафедраси ўқитувчиси, катта лейтенант. Илмий мутахассислиги: 12.00.13 – Инсон ҳуқуқлари. ORCID: 0000-0003-3990-1191.
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Мақолада Инсон ҳуқуқларини таъминлаш ва муҳофаза қилишда давлат органларининг роли, Инсон ҳуқуқларини таъминлаш ва муҳофаза қилишда ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш органларининг ахамияти, Инсон ҳуқуқлари бўйича миллий институтлар, Инсон ҳуқуқларини ҳимоя қилишда Омбудсман институтининг ўрни, Инсон ҳуқуқларини мониторинг қилиш ва келгуси чоралар бўйича миллий институтлар фаолиятини белгилаш, Инсон ҳуқуқлари бўйича Ўзбекистон Республикаси Миллий маркази фаолияти, Миллий превентив механизм қийноқларни олдини олиш механизми, Нодавлат нотижорат ташкилотларининг инсон ҳуқуқларини таъминлаш ва ҳимоя қилишдаги ролини янада ривожлантиришнинг устуворлигини таъминлашга қаратилган қатор таклиф ва тавсиялар илгари сурилган.

Annotation

The article provides recommendations for enhancing the role of state institutions in ensuring and protecting human rights, the importance of human rights protection institutions, national institutions for human rights, the role of the Ombudsman institution in protecting human rights, identifying the activities of national institutions for future challenges, the activities of the National Center of the Republic of Uzbekistan on human rights, the national preventive mechanism for preventing torture, and improving the effectiveness of non-governmental human rights organizations in ensuring and protecting human rights.

Key words: "rights" and "freedom", Ombudsman, human rights, UN, political rights, economic and social rights, "national institutions", "Universal Declaration of Human Rights", "Convention on Human Rights".

In the decades following the adoption of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, various international organizations such as the UN, OSCE, OIC, UNESCO, Council of Europe, and OAS have adopted many important fundamental documents that have further developed the rules for education in the field of human rights based on the principles of humanism. In particular, on November 19, 1974, the UNESCO General Conference adopted a

recommendation on the promotion of international understanding, cooperation and a culture of peace, as well as respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms. The General Conference recommended to all member states of UNESCO that educational institutions responsible for primary and secondary education, as well as institutions responsible for higher and non-formal education, work together with youth and adults in educational activities, involve students and young people in associations of parents, teachers' unions, and other interested parties.

The United Nations, in accordance with the principles set forth in its Charter, has adopted an international bill on human rights and defined the scope of inalienable human rights.

The international bill on human rights consists of five parts, including:

- The Universal Declaration of Human Rights adopted in 1948;
- The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights adopted in 1966;
- The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights adopted in 1966;
- The First Optional Protocol adopted in 1966, which declares the right to lodge complaints;
- The Second Optional Protocol adopted in 1989, which relates to the abolition of the death penalty.

The adoption of the international bill on human rights is seen as a milestone in the development of a contemporary concept of human rights and the advancement of international law on human rights.

International human rights instruments have been established to regulate relations on human rights between states and other subjects of international law, as well as to ensure compliance with human rights in various international documents, whether single, dual, or interconnected, and to be considered binding and enforceable under international law with a clear name and formulated in writing.

When referring to international standards in the field of human rights, the term "international human rights standards" refers to a system of international legal norms that strengthen and promote the realization of human rights and freedoms. First and foremost, these standards oblige states to ensure the fundamental rights and freedoms of their citizens, prevent any actions harmful to their rights and freedoms, not tolerate any forms of discrimination, as well as impose an obligation to take necessary measures to advance human rights and

freedoms against any violations. In addition, through these standards, states are held accountable for failing to fulfill their obligations adequately, and mechanisms of international law have been established to protect human rights and freedoms.

These standards are universal, meaning they are recognized worldwide (normative acts adopted by the UN), as well as regional, having force within a specific region (such as the European Union, Council of Europe, OAS, and AU).

Regional standards mainly focus on their specificity and the responsibility of non-compliant states within a certain region.

International standards are recognized internationally at the international level as universal (in the form of rules, normative acts adopted by the UN) and regional standards that are implemented within certain regions, usually under the auspices of specific international organizations (such as the European Council, the European Union, the OAS, and others). Regional standards are usually more specific and are considered standards that hold non-compliant states within regional organizations accountable.

International standards can take the form of declarations, international treaties (pacts and conventions), resolutions of international organizations, and guiding principles.

Declarations are usually adopted by states' bodies as final documents of their meetings (for example, a resolution of the UN General Assembly) and do not have binding force. Declarations serve to outline directions for further development of international relations in a particular field. States may align their domestic legal documents with the norms of declarations, but it is not mandatory.

The protection of human rights within the international system is based on international treaties (conventions) – pacts and conventions. Such international legal instruments are of universal importance for all states that have ratified and acceded to them. International organizations or their separate bodies are established to monitor compliance with the terms of treaties based on conventions

The international agreements that ensure the general protection of human rights include the following:

1. Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948);
2. International Covenants on Human Rights (1966);
3. International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights (1966);

4. Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide (1948);
5. Convention relating to the Status of Refugees (1951);
6. International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (1965);
7. Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (1979);
8. Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman, or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (1984);
9. Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989) and others.

As examples of regional instruments, the European Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms adopted on November 4, 1950, and entered into force in 1953, supplemented by 14 Additional Protocols; the European Social Charter adopted on October 18, 1961, entered into force in 1965 and revised in 1991; the European Social Charter adopted on November 22, 1969; the American Convention on Human Rights adopted in 1978; the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights adopted in July 1981; the Cairo Declaration on Human Rights in Islam adopted on August 5, 1990; the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities adopted in 1995; the Arab Charter on Human Rights adopted on May 22, 2004; and the Arab Charter on Human Rights adopted on March 15, 2008.

As examples of regional documents, we can mention the Final Act of the Conference on Security and Cooperation in Europe adopted in Helsinki on August 1, 1975; the Vienna Document of the Conference on Security and Cooperation in Europe adopted on January 15, 1989; and the Paris Charter for a New Europe adopted in 1990.

Similarly, the 1990 Copenhagen Document (the document of the Conference on the Human Dimension of the CSCE, Copenhagen Meeting) is considered as the first comprehensive document on human rights within the framework of the OSCE, encompassing the important commitments of participating States in the field of human rights. Emphasizing that the protection and promotion of human rights constitute one of the main objectives of participating States, it is considered that respect for human rights is essential for freedom, justice, and peace. The document sets out several human rights and fundamental freedoms (such as the right to conduct meetings and demonstrations peacefully, the right to use one's property freely, children's rights, and the rights of national minorities) that have not been officially

confirmed within the OSCE before. The Copenhagen Document expanded the scope of human rights commitments by introducing obligations related to elections for human rights monitoring.

Cultural relativism is a methodological approach that is based on the differences that are perceived as clear in certain local cultures, and it rejects universal, global values and norms. Cultural relativism in the context of the application of human rights argues that the rights enshrined in the Western culture cannot be considered universal and therefore denies their universality.

Supporters of cultural relativism in the context of the application of human rights are mainly found among Asian countries, especially China and Iran, as well as among legal and political scholars. They use this methodological approach as evidence against criticism that human rights are being violated in their countries, usually accepted by international organizations.

It is possible to add to the opinion of those who reject all methods of interpreting human rights based on national psychology and local characteristics. Such interpretations can lead to justifying human rights abuses until they begin to serve the purpose of justifying them. Moreover, such interpretations may lead to a complete transition to a legal idealism different from cultural relativism, according to A. Saidov [2].

One of the distinctive features of human rights in the 21st century is their universality. Various cultures and traditions have recognized this universal nature of human rights in the ancient world. The universality of human rights can be seen in the following aspects:

Firstly, the norm-creating process in the field of human rights has been continuously evolving and has not yet reached its peak. Human rights and international norms in this field are closely related to the future development, primarily the states' involvement. Therefore, it is necessary to consider some kind of mechanism that has been designated in advance for the universality of human rights. In other words, although human rights are naturally related to all individuals and peoples, they are based on international norm-creating, as well as the importance of national and regional characteristics, taking into account various historical, social, and religious contexts.

Secondly, human rights are not limited to a specific period or region of political progress. That is, it is not only the product of the modern West but also creates principles regarding human rights in other cultures, traditions, and religions. These principles have played a significant and fundamental role in creating, accepting, and completing contemporary human rights in this field.[3]

Drawing on the above, it is possible to conclude that in the 21st century, amidst the rapid globalization process, the issue of cooperation among states in the field of human rights is becoming increasingly intertwined with both their internal and external policies. In this regard, this situation not only highlights theoretical discussions but also brings to light practical issues aimed at resolving these challenges. Resolving these issues is a fundamental task of international human rights within the framework of the separate field that human rights law has evolved into.

When it comes to universalism in the field of human rights, there is no denying that it has been achieved to a certain extent today. Universalism sheds light on international human rights, explaining and promoting a more comprehensive acceptance of them. The absence of such comprehensive acceptance is confirmed by the fact that universalism continues to be a subject of debate within the UN's human rights agenda.

In the legal state-building process, the Republic of Uzbekistan has defined ensuring human rights and freedoms as a fundamental task in its national legislation. Strengthening the sovereignty of state governance and confirming the priority of rights establishes the cornerstone of legal state-building, demonstrating its direct relevance.

On August 31, 1991, Uzbekistan declared its independence and began the formation of the basic state institutions based on the principle of separation of powers in legislation, execution, and judicial systems. In order to successfully develop social-economic and political-legal relations, the necessity arose to align the national system on human rights and freedoms with the principles and norms of international law recognized by the international community. The following factors contributed to this:

Firstly, Uzbekistan's internal and external policy choices for its development and progress;

Secondly, Uzbekistan's participation in universal international organizations, including the UN and its specialized agencies, as well as active involvement in the activities of key regional international organizations;

Thirdly, Uzbekistan's accession to the main international human rights instruments and, first of all, to the six core international human rights treaties of the UN.

It should be noted that the development of systems and mechanisms for protecting human rights is not only the responsibility of a single state or international organization. The main task of independent Uzbekistan is to

unconditionally fulfill international obligations in the field of human rights and to establish a democratic legal state.

Conclusion

While it is possible for all countries to adhere to international standards, some countries have chosen to apply their own national legal systems in practice, and certain standards are considered to be more applicable to specific countries and are implemented to a higher degree on an international scale. For example, some institutions historically emerged, leaned towards other countries, and operated within a certain timeframe before aligning with internationally recognized standards. In this regard, it is not necessarily accurate to consider international standards as a one-size-fits-all approach that must be implemented in every separate country. International standards play a vital role in defining the direction of developing the legal system of various institutions within a country, particularly in advancing the rule of law, including the judiciary.

The preamble of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan emphasizes the priority of international legal norms over national laws. This constitutional provision establishes that if discrepancies arise between the laws and codes of Uzbekistan and the relevant rules in international treaties, the provisions of the international treaty shall prevail. Overall, Uzbekistan recognizes the importance of adhering to international standards and is committed to upholding human rights and promoting the rule of law within its borders.

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